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Search for high-mass dark matter axion at IBS-CAPP

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Abstract

The axion is a hypothetical pseudo-Goldstone boson proposed to dynamically resolve the strong CP problem, a long-standing mystery in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) of particle physics. In particular, the QCD axions with masses on the order of μeV to meV are a strong candidate for dark matter. The cavity haloscope is one of the most effective techniques to search for dark matter axions in the microwave region. A large cavity volume and low detector noise are crucial for high-frequency axion searches to improve experimental performance. Various novel cavity designs (based on multiple-cell design, wheel mechanism, and tunable photonic crystals) have been developed by IBS-CAPP for efficient searches for high-mass axions. Josephson parametric amplifiers developed by U. of Tokyo/RIKEN achieved near-quantum-limited performance. Utilizing these key components, CAPP is currently conducting leading haloscope experiments to explore the frequency range between 5 GHz and 25 GHz ($20 \mu\text{eV}$ and $100 \mu\text{eV}$) with KSVZ sensitivity. In this talk, we present the current status of these experiments and discuss future plans.

1 Introduction

Even the triumph of the Standard Model (SM), several enduring puzzles remain, one of which is the strong Charge-Parity (CP) problem. This problem pertains to the perplexingly minuscule electric dipole moment of the neutron d_n [1],

$$d_n = 3 \times 10^{-16} \bar{\theta}_{\text{QCD}} [e \cdot \text{cm}] < 1.8 \times 10^{-26} [e \cdot \text{cm}], \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\theta}_{\text{QCD}} = \theta_{\text{QCD}} + \text{DetArg}(M_q)$ is sum of two independent phase originated from θ_{QCD} vacua and phase of quark mass matrix. In 1977, R. Peccei and H. Quinn proposed a solution to the strong CP problem by introducing an auxiliary global axial $U(1)$ symmetry, dynamically canceling the $\bar{\theta}_{\text{QCD}}$ with the Goldstone boson axion in order to minimize the potential [2]. Intriguingly, if this QCD axion is invisible (QCD axion has sufficiently low mass), it can serve as a promising candidate for cold dark matter (CDM) [3]. The potential mass range for the QCD axion to be CDM is constrained to

$$1 \mu\text{eV} \lesssim m_a \lesssim 10 \text{meV}, \quad (2)$$

with the upper bound imposed by astrophysical observations and the lower bound informed by cosmological scenarios of axion existence in the Universe [4]. The primary method for CDM axion detection is the axion cavity haloscope, which uses a resonator cavity within a multi-tesla magnet to resonantly detect photons resulting from axion-photon interactions [5]. Current cavity-haloscope searches are conducted globally by collaborations such as ADMX, HAYSTAC, and IBS-CAPP. As mass m_a and coupling $g_{a\gamma\gamma}$ of axion are unknown, axion haloscopes must tune the resonant frequency of their cavities to search CDM axion. Consequently, the axion haloscope experiments need to maximize the scanning rate df/dt (how fast tune the resonant frequency with the given acquisition time). The scanning rate is expressed as [6]:

$$\frac{df}{dt} \propto \frac{g_{a\gamma\gamma}^4 B_0^4 V^2 C^2}{(T_{\text{eff}} + T_a)^2} \frac{Q_L Q_a}{Q_L + Q_a}, \quad (3)$$

where the terms $B_0, V, C, Q_L, Q_a, T_{\text{eff}}$, and T_a respectively denote the static magnetic field for axion photon interaction, cavity volume, form factor (indicates how much axion induced electric field is aligned to the static magnetic field), loaded quality factor of the cavity, axion quality factor (with a default value of 10^6 for galactic dark matter axions), effective temperature (determined by physical temperature and frequency), and the added noise temperature from the readout chain. To enhance the scanning rate, one can utilize high-field magnets combined with large-volume, high-quality-factor cavities, resonant modes with high form factors, and quantum limit amplifiers to minimize system noise. Figure 1 shows the axion parameter space regarding the axion-photon interaction, explored by various axion haloscope experiments specified to mass range of $1 \mu\text{eV} \lesssim m_a \lesssim 0.1 \text{meV}$. The most sensitive axion searches lie in the low-frequency region, below $10 \mu\text{eV}$. For these low-mass axion searches, enhancing the scanning rate using a standard cylindrical cavity, which encompasses a significant volume, is relatively direct. The mass of axion is predicted from diverse axion production scenarios during the early universe [7, 8, 9, 10], and these models calculate a QCD axion mass predominantly in the high-mass range above 5 GHz. However, with conventional cavity modes, the scanning rate correlates with frequency as $df/dt \propto \omega_0^{-20/3}$, making the search for high-mass axions particularly daunting. Thus, it is necessary to design a novel cavity that can retain volume without compromising on either the high form factor or quality factor.

Figure 1: Current status of cavity haloscope searches in the axion parameter space, including preliminary results from CAPP, highlighted within the range $1\mu\text{eV} \lesssim m_a \lesssim 0.1\text{meV}$.

2 Novel cavity design developed at IBS-CAPP

IBS-CAPP is pioneering the development of various novel cavities with proper frequency tuning mechanism efficient for high-mass axion searches without compromising volume and scanning rate. The institute has mainly proposed three novel cavity designs: the multi-cell cavity [11], wheel cavity [12], and photonic crystal cavity [13]. Figure 2 illustrates the tuning mechanics of these cavities.

Figure 2: Electric field distributions of the cavity designs developed at IBS-CAPP for high-mass axion detection: (a) multi-cell cavities (b) wheel cavity (c) photonic crystal cavity.

The multi-cell (MC) cavity, depicted in Fig. 2(a), subdivides a conventional cylindrical cavity with metal partitions, enabling the exploitation of the higher modes. This design minimizes volume loss, and the central gap facilitates a streamlined detection chain via a single antenna. Moreover, this central gap fortifies the design against tolerances that might induce field localization. However, the MC cavity design does possess constraints regarding resonance frequency enhancement. The design on the right hand of Fig. 2 (a) presents an improved design over the original one, wherein the metal partition is detached from the cavity wall, allowing the electric field to occupy more volume. Figure 3 shows a comparison of the cavity parameters between original MC cavity and new cavity, including Q factor, form factor, and figure of merit. The new design facilitates communication between the electric fields in each chamber, minimizing field localization issues. Moreover, it achieves a higher form factor than the original design, as shown in Fig. 3(a). This high form factor turns into a higher figure of merit (faster scanning speed) than the original design Fig. 3(b). This is advantageous for the form factor, and it offers enhanced robustness against tolerances.

The wheel cavity, shown in Fig. 2(b), utilizes higher-order modes and minimizes form factor degradation by incorporating a structure of a double-layer dielectric rings

Figure 3: Comparison of the original and the improved (new) MC cavities over the same frequency range.

where opposing helicity field profiles arise. With these dielectric rings, the Q-factor of cavity can be augmented. Frequency tuning is achieved by rotating one layer with respect to the other to change the electric field configuration, analogous to a motion of wheel. However, this wheel cavity possesses limited tunability, approximately 5%.

The third design, as seen in Fig. 2(c), named the tunable photonic crystal (PhC) cavity, incorporates a periodic structure of dielectric rods inside the cavity to amplify the resonance frequency. The distance between neighboring rods dictates the resonance frequency, and frequency tuning is feasible through an auxetic structure. This design minimizes volume loss and substantially enhances the Q-factor through the multiple dielectric rods. Nonetheless, this design presents challenges related to mode mixing within the designated tuning range.

IBS-CAPP has successfully pioneered these novel cavity designs. Utilizing a 2-cell cavity and an original 6-cell MC cavity, IBS-CAPP has conducted axion haloscope experiments at frequencies of 3 GHz and 6 GHz [14, 15].

Figure 4: Demonstration of the novel cavity designs by obtaining mode maps at 4K for (a) the wheel cavity and (b) the tunable photonic crystal cavity.

In addition to the MC cavity, we have successfully demonstrated the tuning mechanisms of both the wheel cavity and the PhC cavity at a cryogenic temperature of 4K, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Furthermore, an experiment utilizing a PhC cavity with 21 dielectric posts is under preparation, aiming to detect axions with a mass around 10 GHz.

3 On going experiment at CAPP for high mass axion search

At IBS-CAPP, a high-mass axion search experiment is underway using the advanced MC cavity design (with three chambers), coupled with a Josephson Parametric Amplifier (JPA) developed by Prof. Nakamura's group from the University of Tokyo. The JPA is a quantum limit amplifier exhibiting a noise temperature nearing the standard quantum limit. We utilize a superconducting magnet made of Nb₃Sb with a bore size of 96 mm and this superconducting magnet provides a 12 T magnetic field to the cavity. All of the experimental apparatus are cooled by the dilution refrigerator system, and the cavity and the JPA can reach temperature of 40 mK. The experiment is named CAPP-12T-MC. For the cavity of CAPP-12T-MC, we employed an enhanced version of the original MC cavity. For this cavity geometry, we optimized parameters such as partition wall thickness, cavity height, and tuning rod diameter to maximize the figure of merit. Figure 5 presents the simulated quality factor and form factor for this optimized design.

Figure 5: Simulated quality factor (Q) and form factor (C) for the optimized cavity geometry.

We assessed the noise temperature of the JPA across its operational frequency range, spanning from 5.1 GHz to 5.35 GHz, at 200 kHz intervals. At singular JPA resonant frequencies, the noise temperature was gauged using the spectrum comparison method with a 5 MHz frequency span. Figure 6 showcases the evaluated JPA added noise and the corresponding JPA gain.

Figure 6: Measured JPA added noise (top) and gain (bottom).

Around the resonant frequency of 5.3 GHz, we observed the noise temperature to be approximately 0.2 K. Utilizing this noise temperature data and the cavity

profile, the scanning rate was estimated for KSVZ axions. For the frequency range between 5.29 and 5.34 GHz, the typical scanning rate of 1 MHz/day was achieved. Thus, it would necessitate around 50 days of experimental work to cover the range with KSVZ sensitivity. Currently, the CAPP-12T-MC experiment is in the DAQ mode for axion dark matter search. Through the experiment, we can also examine specific axion production scenarios that posit the mass within the 5.3 GHz range.

4 Conclusion

The QCD axion production scenarios predict the presence of high-mass axions, particularly those with frequencies exceeding 5 GHz. Traditional searches, for example, using the conventional cavity haloscope, face challenges in detecting these high-mass axions. To address this, IBS-CAPP has developed a variety of innovative cavity designs with specialized tuning mechanisms. Among these are the MC cavity, wheel cavity, and the tunable PhC crystal cavity. We have successfully showcased these state-of-the-art cavities, and they have been instrumental in our dark matter axion searches. Currently, CAPP is conducting the CAPP-12T-MC experiment to search for high-mass axions, targeting a frequency range of 5.3 GHz using an advanced version of the MC cavity. To enhance the precision of this search, we have integrated a JPA as our primary amplifier. This has led to a remarkable reduction in added noise temperature, achieving $T_{\text{add}} = 0.2 K$ within the targeted frequency. With these technological advancements, we anticipate achieving a sensitivity of 1 KSVZ in the 5.29 – 5.34 GHz range. These efforts not only highlight the CAPP’s commitment to the search for axions but also address our capability to leverage cutting-edge technologies in pursuit to unravel fundamental mysteries of the universe.

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